

Non-native Finnish speaker?

Participate in a spoken
interaction study!

**Aasis research project –
developing automatic
assessment of
spoken interaction**

University of Helsinki, Aalto University,
University of Jyväskylä
Research Council of Finland (2023-2027)

Who?

If you speak Finnish as a second
or foreign language, welcome!

Why participate?

- All kinds of speakers are needed
- We are interested in your opinion
- Support development of an online tool
- Contribute to science
- You get a Finnkinno movie ticket

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How do I participate?

Data collection in: Room DICE-3,
Konemiehentie 1, Espoo

Duration: 1 h

Contact: ext-ilona.lahteenmaki@aalto.fi
and we'll set up a time for you!

**You can also participate
with a friend!**

**A big
thank you
for your time**

For more information

bit.ly/aasisinfo